
Emerging Trends in Sustainability of Organic Farming and its Impact on Purchase Intention - A Review & Research Agenda

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ABSTRACT

The farming of organic product is a unique practice which balances the environmental sustainability and also controls the detrimental effect both on customer's safety by creating a positive notion in the minds of the customers. The study is basically related to growing of Organic farm products and its influence towards customer attitude which leads to purchase intention. This Research has considered certain variables such as Health Concern, Perceived Behavioural Control, perception of customers, Subjective Norms and Environmental Concerns as to the antecedents of purchase intention. The objective of the literature review is to assess the sustainability factor of organic farm products both in India and abroad and also to identify the impact on customers buying behaviour along with exploring the demand factor in present and future scenarios and identifying the customer's attitude and environmental concern. This literature review is developed by using the secondary data collected from exhaustive literature, review of journals and the internet. The purpose of the study is to identify the customer's environmental concern and commitment towards environment sustainability. In organic farming, there is an advantage of low-cost input prices in production which diverts the attention of customers towards organic farming. The limitation of the study is the people are more motivated by personal factors rather than social or environmental factors. The study is limited to organic farm products and customers' attitude leading to purchase intention.

Keywords: Organic farm products, Environmental sustainability, Purchase intention, Health concern, perceived behavioural control, Perception of customers, Subjective norms, Environmental concern, Customer attitude, Organic farming.

1. Introduction:

India had an exposure towards farm productivity over several decades is now facing scarcity of inputs for the cultivation of agriculture farm products. The usages of synthetic fertilizers ravage the crop and resources and non-sustainability which thereby reduce the productivity of agriculture crops. The industrialization process also had lead to a reduction in agriculture land areas. The over-utilization of resources and soil degradation has also lead to crop failure and the forest has been reduced by deforestation. The environmental issue is a growing concern among the present generation and hence recycled products have gained more attention. To solve the Non-sustainability of resources the one solution is to encounter this problem and focus towards organic food products in Indian soil and thereby maintaining the ecological balance and eradicating the bad effects of people's choice on non-organic products. The organic farming method is less harmful to the crops since synthetic fertilizers are not used in this process [1]. To increase the demand the government should play a pivotal role in adopting awareness programs and assimilate various steps in promoting these products and thereby provide subsidy for the organic crop producing farmers. The government has suggested various schemes from the past period of 2003-2014 [2]. The customers are more discerning towards environmental issues show the tendency to adopt organic practices and also concerned about the health issue which too they consider as a primary factor. The agriculture sector is dependent on climate, where the atmospheric problem and warm temperature along with wind conditions and heavy rainfall show the serious effect on soil erosion and thereby the producers of organic crops have to retrench the expenses of production and replenish the supply for further productivity. Moreover, best practices should be utilized in order to eradicate the bad effects of climate change [4]. The urban sector customers are more aware of the product and it is the duty of the organic producers to bring innovation and retain modification [5]. When compared to conventional product organic product prices are higher and out of reach of common man, Moreover people lack knowledge. So it is a duty to alert society and tackle the problem before it jeopardizes the environment and provides a healthy tomorrow [6].

2. Objectives of the study:

This study is limited to the sustainability of organic farming and its impact on purchase intention. The main objectives are:

- (1) To investigate the sustainability of organic farming in India and abroad.
- (2) To analyze the impact of organic farm products leading to the purchase intention of the customer.
- (3) To explore the demand of organic farm products in the present and future.
- (4) To identify the attitude and environmental awareness of customers towards organic farm products.

2.1 Organic farming and sustainability:

India is one of the second largest production houses for producing synthetic fertilizers and pesticides compared to China in the Asian continent. Studies show that 90% of the pesticides sprayed on the plants never reach its target whereas it is emitted to the air, soil, and water and it takes several centuries to recover from such carbon losses [7].

Conventional farming was the most popular farming earlier since people were unaware of soil loss and environmental degradation. To encounter this problem organic farming was introduced which was an untapped market in the beginning. In order to maintain an ecological balance between life and environment and thereby meeting the food demand and increase the soil fertility with soil organic carbon, educating people and creating awareness became crucial through imparting information about the detrimental effect of nonorganic cultivation [8]. In order to maintain the sustainability of resource, many farmers practice the usage of crop rotation in different cycles. It may be a two-year rotation or three-year rotation such as cover cropping and also green manure. Crop rotation usage increases the fertility of the soil. These practices have encouraged the farmers to retrench cost [9]. The practice of crop rotation has emerged from earlier decades, the farmers grow the crops in a row on the same land area and legumes were been used as green manure. During the period of the Roman civilization, the crop rotation strategy has gained more value since it acts as a protective measure in maintaining the ecological balance, moisture in the soil and sustains productivity and protects the fertility of soil unlike conventional farming [10]. According to the survey of Indian Institute of Social Science revealed the productivity of organic crop compared to the convention is lower by 9.2% but the cost of cultivation of organic crops is less compared to conventional which was about 11.7% moreover profit earned by organic production was more than conventional which is about 22.0% [11].

2.2 Climate change:

Climate change plays a significant role in the non-sustainability and sustainability of resources in both developing and developed economies. The sustainability will outlast only when climatic condition favour the crops [12]. During the hot weather, high annual rainfall and very poor soil quality require better practices and techniques in the sustainability of agriculture crops. The different cropping systems such as diversified systems, mono-cropping systems may devastate the fertility of soil and imbalance the ecology to a much higher extent than in the temperate climates since the soil oxidation and pest population is higher in tropical regions. The heavy rainfalls in these regions jeopardize the available nutrients and minerals in the soil. In order to endeavor the soil fertility, the farmers try to cover the soil with plant and animal waste. The soil containing organic residues naturally retain more water in the soil and the water-retaining capacity range from 20-40% which is comparatively higher than conventional product [13].

The pesticides sprayed in aircraft may damage the whole ecosystem and affect the agriculture areas and thereby the climatic condition. The pesticides sprayed towards the ground are carried towards the water and remain in water which may ravage the water resource. Approximately 80% of the sprayed pesticides remain in the soil and 20% will reach target [14]. The use of synthetic fertilizers and harmful chemicals pose a higher risk to human health and the environment. The Pesticides and Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) residues impose heavy damage to the crops, soil, water, air, living beings, etc. Since these chemicals disseminate in the soil for a long time and eventually they decompose and are later absorbed by the crop grown on it. The continuous usage of chemical pollutants in the soil may deteriorate the soil fertility. Where the farmers have to increase the quantity of chemical and thereby increase in

the cost of the production and fall in debt trap which eventually lead to an increase in farmers suicide. All these reasons made the farmers shift towards organic cropping [15].

Table 1: List of Top Pesticide Consuming Countries of the World [16].

Rank	Country	Annual Pesticide Consumption (millions of kilograms)
1	China	1,806
2	United States	386
3	Argentina	265
4	Thailand	87
5	Brazil	76
6	Italy	63
7	France	62
8	Canada	54
9	Japan	52
10	India	40

Source: World Atlas

In some of the developing economies, the provision of subsidy by the government is limited moreover chemical fertilizers and pesticides are quite expensive and cheap labour divert their attention towards organic production due to low-cost input price of organic crops. The added benefit is that the crop failure due to natural calamities such as drought, pest damage is low in organic compared to conventional crops. The increase in demand for organic crops has led to the circulation of these crops both in domestic as well as international level. This led to the marketers to venture into organic markets. India is one of the exporters of organic products such as rice, cotton, tea, spices with promising domestic organic markets. Now a day's, customers are more discerning about environmental issues and meticulous about the product they purchase and it is the duty of the government to impart good messages about going organic in society [17]. The small farmers are incoherent with the environmental message, needs a good education about organic practices. Since they constantly use the convention farming methods so as to increase the yield and demand for their crop. But eventually the effect of chemical usage on crops detriment wholly the soil fertility and land may become useless for further cultivation. In 2001 a group of organizations and also the corporate bodies took a major step to set up an Organic Certification Agency, together with its partners provided a center for organic agriculture networking and development of the market sector in India. Where these agencies certification differs based on

different regions and nations [18]. When compared to the world scale during the year 2003 organic products gained a total revenue of 23 billion USD, 2005 it increased to 33 billion USD [19]. From 2006-2007 it increased from 40-60 billion USD [20]. Research analysis of the crucial organic food market in the world with the highest consumption level and Asia is one of the promising markets with a high growth rate annually. Since their diversion is more towards organic consumption [21].

Table 2: List of Countries with Largest Number of Organic Producers [22].

Rank	Country	Number of Organic Farm Operations
1	India	650,000
2	Uganda	191,000
3	Mexico	170,000
4	Philippines	166,000
5	Tanzania	149,000
6	Ethiopia	136,000

Source: World Atlas

The organic food market is emerging its growth around the world at the fastest rate through market trends and segmentation. The growth is about 19% in 2007, due to increasing awareness, health and environmental issue is the main concern. In countries like North America and Europe, there is a tremendous growth of organic products in the organic market [23]. Studies show that customer's main focus on organic food is their personal drive that motivates them for purchase intention which includes environmental issues, awareness and knowledge, health issues, nutrition level and also their emotions [24].

India is a promising market for organic products from the past several years. The export of organic products increased by exporting almost 300 products to 20 different countries with different category products. India's favourable agro-climate, hilly regions rain-fed land areas have led to the growing markets in domestic levels and also increased the export potential of the country. The organic practices in the country have led to a substantial increase in the purchasing power, health consciousness, increase in per-capita income of the country, and consumers demand products. India's organic production started in 1997 in Lucknow now along with more than 1,000 farmers in UP, Andhra Pradesh, and Rajasthan. The companies increase the revenue not only through domestic sales but also through the export of organic products to almost 35-40 countries. The government charismatically should enforce the sustainability of organic practices by empowering the farmers to take a predominant step in going organic and also by establishing support by training and education to the thousands of impoverished cultivators. The company also acts as a mediator by acquiring the necessary certificate and providing to the related farmers. This has resulted in the improvement of organic practices simultaneously [25].

Table 3: Turnover of Top Organic Companies of India (in INR Crore) [26].

Company	Turnover(INR Crore)
Organic India	350
24 letter mantra	200
Morarka "Down to Earth"	128
Conscious Foods	120
Eco farms	85
Nature basket	30
Navdanya	25
Fab India	20
Others	450

Source: Yes Bank Survey 2012

2.3 Organic Farming and customers:

The organic marketers /Companies in order to increase their turnover have to spend more on the advertisement and promotional strategies and impart awareness to the users as well as distributors and thereby endeavor the users about the environmental sustainability [27]. The purchasing intention of customers leads to an increase in the productivity of the organic crops where the need for green manure may increase the demand and replace the synthetic manure by capturing the nitrogen in the atmosphere and developing nutrient level in soil profile [28]. Several principles are followed by the organic producers regarding sustainability, water conservation measures, selection of certified seeds and seedling, the prohibition of chemical usage and thereby reducing the loss of nitrogen, prosperous and other nutrients [29]. The environmental benefit cropping methods such as crop rotation cover cropping system and hydroponics system maintains the fertility and water retention capacity. Hydroponic farming is the farming method where plants are grown without the use of soil, in net pots or some other metal pipes where the organic waste stream is used as a nutrient solution. In other words, it is called soilless gardening.

The high usage of nutrient solutions leads to a toxic effect on plants [30]. The crops grown in Hydroponic are in liquid solution such as the ingredients are clay, coir bricks wood fiber, etc. The crop plants such as tomatoes, beans, eggplant, radish, cucumbers, and peppers and also herbs, medicinal and rose plants. The plants are grown in the top with high nitrogen and phosphorous. Most of the hydroponic farming was developed in Latin America and can be adapted to the urban sector conditions. The plants can be grown without the soil and in small spaces. The water used here is recycled which is pollution resistance and environmental friendly and fresh pesticide-free vegetables are produced [31]. Studies show that some customers of the developing economies are willing to give more prices for conventional products due to a lack of trust in organic product quality. Hence the organic producers in order to tackle these problems the

marketers have to take initiative with the support of the government by assimilating trust and awareness about health and environmental factors. [32].

2.4 Organic demand in the present and future market scenario:

The organic market originated in the nineteenth-century from the niche market to the mainstream market in industrial sectors. The world market for these organic products increased around 43% with an approximate figure of US \$18 billion to the US \$ 23 billion with 40% of the organic cultivators belong to Asia, along with Africa with 28% and Latin America with 16%. The purchasing decision of customers literary based on personal factors such as trust, knowledge and socio-demographic which play an important role in creating more loyalty towards these products [33]. The domestic markets for production of organic is growing higher at a fast range and companies thrive hard to provide the input knowledge to its future customers by trade fairs and exhibitions and Karnataka state have put forth efforts to popularize organic farming’s through its “organic & Millets 2018 international trade fairs” Studies show that the High and middle-income group with higher education have a positive belief about the products which do not contain any chemicals or fertilizers are worth to consume rather than fertilizer based conventional due to this perception that they are willing to pay more [34].

In the present scenario organic farming is considered as a booming industry with health benefits along with environmental factors are considered crucial and government have designed various scheme and programs to provide education to farmers about the organic practices and programs and market linkages for producers and along with the usage of new technologies in farming methods [35]. The people perceive that the export of organic products is more in number than domestic consumption. But 50% of the organic products are consumed more in domestic rather than exported to different nations. The people show more concern towards organic and are ready to pay higher prices because of the health issues of their children. The exports are at a high rate due to an increase in farmers' shift towards organic products. Countries like the US and Europe is the leading market for the export of India’s organic products. India is one of the suppliers of organic herbs, spices, and rice, etc. The price of organic products varies from 20-30% Higher than conventional products [36]. Studies show that the pesticide residue if one of the second largest agents causing cancer [37].

Table 4: The Organic Markets under Retail Sales 2018 [38].

Countries	Retail sales (in Million Euros)
USA	38,938
Germany	9,478
France	6,736
China	5,900
Canada	3,002

Italy	2,644
UK	2,460
Switzerland	2,298
Sweden	1,944
Spain	1,686

Source: FIBL-AMI survey 2018

In the organic food markets, imbalances can be created by the market forces' demand and supply. In order to cope up with the situation, action should be taken meticulously by way of creating an awareness program regarding health and safety. The demand will be at low when the farmers show disinterest in organic practices due to lack of financial accommodation, certification cost, the size of the market and finally the distribution channels. In the organic food markets, the most influential matter is brand equity which leads to consumer buying intention. People are more motivated by personal factors rather than social or environmental factors. This is the reasons the organic market is still small and holistic measure is needed to endeavor this problem [39]. The customer passes along these steps to finalize his purchase intention. Initially, the intention to purchase, collecting information which is linked to their perception, searching for product availability, where to buy and what to buy has become crucial in purchasing decision and finally, all the decision have a direct link towards customers belief, behavior, demographic features and perception [40]. One of the important aspects such as brand levels of organic products has a strong and emotional resonance among the purchaser with regard to health and environmental benefits. The studies conducted show that health issue gains emphasis and a strong motivating factor in organic product purchase [41].

3. Conceptual framework of the study:

Some of the factors which affect the attitude of consumers towards the usage of organic food products are:

3.1 Health Concern:

Today people have more perception that organic foodstuffs have a low level of chemicals with higher nutrient levels. The countries like North America the customer's perception towards organic food products is positive since the main motive is the choice for their family and children for better health prospects [42]. The health concern is growing trends that have a high impact on consumption and also environment sustainability, which has led to increasing purchase intention towards organic foods [43]. Countries like China also have more concern towards health and safety, which has led to the adaptation of three levels of food production which involve safe food, green food and organic food where people are willing to pay more for healthier foods. The researches show that people of China are concerned about health issue are more likely to have a positive attitude in the purchase of organic food products. The health

concern is a more common factor where studies show that the reason for purchasing green products is particularly people are aware of the residues from the pesticides used in conventional agriculture [44]. Consumers' perception towards organic food products is the important motive behind the purchase, where consumer's main concern is health issues [45]. The organic food products and purchase intention of consumers are directly associated with the health concern of consumers [46]. The consumers who are health conscious about their diet are expected to eat or maintain or live a healthy life [47]. The consumer in order to safeguard and to satisfy their nutrition and health needs give more importance to control the cholesterol level and heart-related problems always prefer healthy foods and they stick towards organic food products [48].

3.2 Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC):

Perceived behavioural control refers to maintain behavior related to the perception and their ability. The higher Perceived Behavioural control always contributes towards a positive attitude and leads to sustainable products in real consumption [49]. The individual attitude or belief based on the situation faced and combined with the internal factors leads to perceived behavioural control [50]. When people need to buy an organic food product need information, knowledge, and belief about the products, but the People sometimes do not have control based on situation factors, when he is carrying out a purchase [51]. Studies show that to perform certain behaviour an individual has less control over it due to the lack of needed resources and purchase intention will be lesser even if he has a positive attitude [52]. The customer's level of confidence has led to behavioural control and has a positive relationship with the purchase intention [53]. Perceived behavioural control is one's ability to handle the situation with success [54]. The PBC effectiveness can be identified through various studies that reveal that individual belief in the organic purchase is a positive contribution towards environmental factors [55]. An individual perceived behavioural control depend upon his belief on various occasion [56]. The PBC of an individual is totally dependent on the ability or limitation which he perceives, leading to purchase intention [57].

3.3 Environmental Concern:

The Environmental Concern has prevented the customers from the purchase of environmental hazard products. This attitude has influenced customers' purchasing intentions towards organic products [58]. In order to maintain sustainability, India has banned plastic bags. The growing environmental concern among the companies are emphasizing on environmental friendly products moreover customers also show more interest in these products [59]. The customer's environment concern towards organic products will create a favourable attitude towards the product [60]. The environmental concern and commitment towards environment sustainability lead to control of the depletion of resources and a positive impact on organic purchases [61]. The people with more concern over the environmental issue are willing to pay higher prices for organic products than the people who show less concern towards environment issues [62]. Studies also show that health and environment are the determinants for customer's attitude with regard to organic foods [63]. For several years there has been a demand for organic food products which have led towards environment protection

and an increase in the purchase intention of these products [64]. Several friendly approaches are used in producing organic food products where customers are more aware of the environment which leads to a higher impact on the purchase of organic products [65]. Many customers are showing good judgement towards green products due to high environmental concern by choosing them when purchasing [66]. Urban residents have more tendencies for organic purchases due to environmental concern [67].

3.4 Customers Perception:

The factor which influences the purchase intention is the perception towards eco-friendly products. The positive or negative aspect may lead to changes in purchase intention [68]. The utility of the assessment of the organic product is based on perception and its value is determined about what is received and given [69]. The perception regarding the sustainability of products and safety, freshness, taste along with health concern, environment awareness has lead to the positive attitude of customers towards organic purchases [70]. The people of Thailand perceive that organic can be purchased if it meets the different criteria such as taste, quality, freshness, and nutrition level and food safety [71]. The customers in India have more perception towards eco-friendly issues, environmental concerns and are more predictive towards their organic buying behaviour [72]. The customers purchasing intention is basically influenced by the perceived economic situation such as the price and trust towards the product [73]. Studies show that the perception and motivation of the customers to purchase organic products depend on social, personal and financial aspects [74]. The customer's perceptions regarding the quality of the product can be determined by their past purchasing behaviour, since the satisfaction of the product usage may lead to further purchase intention [75].

3.5 Subjective Norms:

The societal burden for any individual to comply or involved with a set of behaviour such as friends as well as the spouse is defined as subjective forms. Studies reveal that subjective norms have a great impact on the tendency of individual behaviour or attitude which further leads to purchase intention with respect to organic products [76]. The norms and the values learned at home have a great impact on the development of a positive attitude towards organic purchases [77]. The individual who involves in group behaviour along with family and friends have a great influence on consumer attitude for going organic [78]. The customers believe that if others think organic products are better they may intend to purchase them due to social pressure [79]. The subjective norms influence a person's purchase intention due to the opinion of the close ones [80]. Based on the observation of very close people, a favourable attitude can be achieved which may lead to purchase intention [81]. The subjective norm is considered as a social pressure which intends an individual in specific behaviour and motivates him for further purchase [82].

3.6 Attitude:

The attitude towards a purchase intention is the behavioural outcome of an individual buying behaviour [83-85]. A positive attitude emphasizes purchase intention based on

the level of income, education, etc and also believes in organic foods due to taste, healthier, and environmental benefits [86]. Attitude towards organic food products is an essential aspect of customers' buying intention [87]. Studies show favourable attitude towards organic brands will increase the buying intention of customers [88]. The adoption of organic food product usage by customers shows that positive perception leads to the fulfillment of purchase intention [89]. The customers basically choose the organic product based on the positive health issue, environment-friendly, and better taste. So naturally, the purchase intention of these products is based on beliefs about benefits [90]. When compared to other variables a predictor of behaviour always tries to reduce the harmful effect on the environment. So meticulously he involves in the purchase intention of organic food products [91]. Social psychological research shows that attitude is the mediator of both behaviour and intention to purchase [92]. Based on planned behaviour theory the customer's belief and perceptions lead to purchase intention [93]. The individual attitude needs to be changed in order to convert his behaviour towards pro-environmental issues [94]. A comfortable perception towards organic products may result in a positive attitude [95].

3.7 Purchase Intention:

The customers with high value about the attitude towards the environment are found to be high scorers and have high intentions to purchase [96]. The individual who gives value towards organic purchases is influenced by the belief in safety and health concern which leads to purchasing behaviour [97]. The purchase intention is the situation where the customers wish to involve in the purchase of organic farm products [98]. Purchase intention is a subjective judgment made by the customers after the evaluation of the products in order to purchase the products [99]. An individual can increase his purchase intention towards organic products through propaganda and advertisement given in different media and develop a brand attachment towards that product [100]. The knowledge about the product, the attributes of the products may lead to the purchase intention of a customer [101]. The word of mouth is one of the motivating factors for the increase in the purchase intention of organic products [102]. Studies show that loyalty is a prevailing reason for the regular purchase of organic products [103].

4. Observation-based on review:

- (1) The people show more concern towards organic and are willing to pay the higher premium due to the perceived health issues.
- (2) The environmental concern and commitment towards environment sustainability lead to control of the depletion of resources and a positive impact on organic purchases.
- (3) The reports reveal that the exports are at a high rate due to an increase in farmers' shift towards organic products. Countries like the US and Europe are the leading market for the export of India's organic products. India is one of the suppliers of organic herbs, spices, and rice, etc.

(4) Studies show that customer's main focus on organic food is their personal drive that motivates them for purchase intention which includes environmental issues, awareness and knowledge, health issues, nutrition level and also their emotions.

(5) The domestic markets for the production of organic are growing higher at a fast range and companies thrive hard to impart beneficial knowledge to the buyers by trade fairs and exhibitions and Karnataka state have put forth efforts to popularize organic farming practices.

(6) From the study, we notice that the incentives provided by the government are very limited and it is found that in conventional farming the chemical fertilizers and pesticides used are quite expensive.

5. Research gap:

The following section describes constructs relating to a health concern, subjective norms, environmental concern, perceived behavioural control, perception, and attitude aspects which the prior research has used as antecedents of purchase intention. While arriving at the research gap, the analytical process adopted by this research endeavour contains the following steps: First, categorize all the independent variable to identify which indicate purchase intention. The main objective is to investigate the constructs which fit the model of purchase intention. Secondly, trying to understand the variable which is suitable for research analysis. Selecting this approach and moving towards the research gap. The following research gaps are observed subjected to find out the independent variables of the purchase intention.

Research gap 1: Health concern, attitude and purchase Intention

Prior research has shown that in North America people have more concern towards their children's and family health which induced them to buy organic products [42]. Prior research has also shown that the health concern of individuals also has a high impact on purchase intention and environmental sustainability [43]. Research in China has concentrated on three aspects namely safe food, green food, and organic food in connection with health and safety. It is the health concern that is responsible for developing a positive attitude and motivating purchase intention among the consumers [44]. The organic food products and purchase intention of customers are directly associated with the health concern of the customer. Prior research has also investigated the impact of health consciousness [46], health issues [45], healthy life [47], and health [48], on individual attitude and purchase intention of customers. However, there exists a dearth of studies that have investigated health concerns that affect individuals as well as organizations. There is no prior research endeavour has investigated the direct effect of health concern on attitude and purchase intention, when it is conceptualized. Therefore, the present research endeavour addresses this research gap by investigating the impact of health concern on attitude and purchase intention. Accordingly, this research endeavour proposes the antecedent and consequence relationship among behavioural/ perceptual variables only. It may be noted that the construct of purchase intention is conceptualized as a behavioural/ perceptual construct. Hence, the following research question:

What are the various issues of health concern influences consumer purchase intention and how corporate should identify the right health concern issues to increase the purchase intention of individuals?

Research gap 2: Perceived behavioural control, attitude and purchase Intention

Prior research highlights that Perceived behavioural control contributes towards a positive attitude and leads to sustainable products in real consumption [49]. Several studies have dwelt on attitude and purchase intention of individuals is based on Perceived behavioural control on a situation basis [50], on information, belief and knowledge [51]. Against this background, empirical research has shown that Perceived behavioural control is though responsible for changing the individual attitude and purchase intention towards buying organic products but also motivates individuals towards environmental concern [55]. An individual perceived behavioural control of an individual is mainly depends on different occasions [56], the confidence level of the customers [53], the ability of an individual's [54], and limitations individual perceives [57]. However, there is no prior study has investigated the direct effect of Perceived behavioural control on attitude and purchase intention. Hence, the following research question:

What are the different issues involved in Perceived behavioural control and its impact on individual attitude and purchase intention?

Research gap 3: Perception, attitude and purchase Intention:

Prior research states that consumer attitude and purchase intention will be positive when they are perceived that the products are organic and environmental friendly [104]. Past research also highlights that when the consumer has a positive perception towards a healthy product, safe product, and the environmentally friendly product definitely they buy it [105]. Whenever consumer's perception of organic products is eco-friendly there is no doubt it changes consumers' attitude and purchase intention [106]. Change in the purchase intention [107], depends on individual personal experiences with the products [108]. So it can be concluded that change in the attitude and purchase intention is mainly based on consumer's perception and their experiences with the products. In light of prior research work, the research questions are framed.

What are the different parameters corporate need to make consumers perception positive towards organic products and thereby change their attitude and purchase intention?

Research gap 4: Subjective Norms, attitude and purchase Intention

Research in the artificial apparel industry indicates that subjective norms have a very strong and important relationship with attitude as well as on consumer purchase intention [109]. Subjective norms also play a functional role in changing attitude as well as the purchase intention of an individual [110], escalate purchase intention [111], and create a social image. Prior research indicates that subjective norms change the attitude of an individual depends on the types of products and thereby affect the purchase intention of an individual. Subjective norms are predictors of organic product

consumption and the environmental behaviors of individuals [112]. Based on prior research the following research question has been framed:

How corporate can effectively measure subjective norms by taking into consideration a) Close friends and family, b) The people who I listen and c) Important people in my life?

Research gap 5: Environmental concern, attitude and purchase intention

Empirical studies have investigated the unique and parsimonious stepping stone in changing attitudes and purchase intention of the consumers. Research states that people are ready to pay more prices for an organic product if they are concerned about environmental aspects [62]. Prior research also states that there is a strong relationship between environmental protection and attitude as well as purchase intention [64]. Research also highlights that change in the consumer attitude and purchase intention is possible through environmental [65-67]. Research also states that for the sustainability of organic product it is just that products need to be environmentally friendly [59] which creates favourable attitude [60]. However, the paucity of empirical research, in this regard, calls for testing empirically the theoretically articulated relationship between the constructs of types of environmental concern and attitude as well as purchase intention at an individual level. Therefore, the impact of environmental concern is theoretically expected to strengthen the variables attitude and thereby purchase intention accordingly, this research endeavour considers the construct environmental concern as an antecedent of attitude while building the proposed trust model. Hence the following research question:

What measure corporate needs to take to create environmental friendly feelings in the minds of individuals in order to change their attitude and motivate their purchase intention?

6. Research agenda:

- (1) What are the various issues of health concern influences consumer purchase intention and how corporate should identify the right health concern issues to increase the purchase intention of individuals?
- (2) What are the different issues involved in perceived behavioural control and its impact on the individual attitude and purchase intention of organic products?
- (3) What are the different parameters corporate had to focus to make consumers perception positive towards organic products and thereby change their attitude and purchase intention?
- (4) How corporate can effectively measure subjective norms by taking into consideration (a) Close friends and family, (b) The people who I listen and (c) Important people in my life?
- (5) What measure corporate needs to take to create environmental friendly feelings in the minds of individuals in order to change their attitude and motivate their purchase intention?

7. Suggestions and Recommendations:

(1) In order to maintain an ecological balance between life and environment and thereby meeting the food demand and increasing the soil fertility with soil organic carbon, companies should be educated about the holistic production and creating awareness are crucial through imparting information about the negative effect of nonorganic cultivation.

(2) In order to give a competitive edge to all companies at the global level and also to increase the export, the country should strengthen the concept of organic practices since it is an eye-opener for the country to fetch good price for their product both in the national as well as international level along with provision of education and articulately imparting information about the consequences of inorganic food consumption.

(3) In the developing economies, the subsidy provided by the government to the organic producers is limited. Moreover, the rate of chemical pesticides is quite expensive and steps should be taken by the government to provide financial accommodation and also increase the subsidy for organic crop growing farmers so that they can utilize these opportunities for improving productivity.

(4) The perception of the customers has to lead to substantial growth in the progress of the organic product, where supply is short compared to demand. The reason for this failure is the price of the organic products which are quite higher when compared to conventional products. The impoverished farmers don't opt for organic production due to high labour cost and low demand compared to supply. In this regard, the Government should emphasize some new schemes for organic farmers with regard to incentives and act as a channel in promoting the organic food products in the market.

(5) Since environment issue is a growing concern among the present generation and hence recycled products have gained more attention. This concern may lead to more usage of organic products leading to further demand. But the rural sector lacks information about the environmental factors, which are the reasons they go for conventional crop production. Since they feel they can gain more profits by inorganic farming leading to ravage of environmental soil. The continuous usage of these chemicals may make the soil fertility useless in mere future and wastage of agriculture land areas. To encounter these problems the government should educate the farmers on the negative effect of inorganic farming and its effect on the environment.

8. Conclusion:

The organic food market is emerging as an important area of business throughout the world and growing at a faster rate through market trends and segmentation. The growth is about 19% in 2007, due to the reasons of increasing awareness, health concern, and environmental issue. In countries like North America and Europe, there is a tremendous growth of organic food products in the food market. The organic farming is considered a booming industry with health benefits along with environmental factors that are considered crucial and the government has designed various subsidy schemes and awareness programs to provide education to farmers

about the advantages of organic practices. India's first organic production company Organic India Private Ltd. (OIPL) started in 1997 in Lucknow along with more than 2,000 farmers' involvement from UP, Andhra Pradesh, and Rajasthan. The outlets are been set throughout the country which has increased the company profits. The export share of organic products from India has increased by exporting almost 300 products to 20 different countries with different category products. The customers are more diverted towards environmental issues which show the tendency to adopt organic practices and also concerned about the health issue which too they consider as a primary factor. This has led to the purchase intention of customers towards organic products. The purchasing decision of customers basically depends on internal and external factors including trust, knowledge, and socio-demographic factors which are expected to play an important role in creating demand for organic products.

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